

MAKING A CAREER IN ACADEMICS.

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Abstract

This topic cannot be discussed without talking about the history of the legal profession, legal education and history of the University education globally. I delved into the history of pioneers of law academics in Europe and America because of the immense influence of Euro-American jurisprudence on our legal system. I discussed what is law academics, qualification to become an academic, career progression in law academic and integrity, diligence and hard work as sustaining grace in academic. I concluded the paper by emphasizing the need for role model and mentoring in academic, in order to have a hitch free interface and successful academic career.

THE GENESIS

What is known today as the legal profession started informally in England. The English law itself emerged from common law far back as the 13th century.¹ Then the doctrine of common law was so complex that it needed experts to proffer solutions to them. Since there was no one who was learned in law, **narrators** or **pleaders** arose or developed.² They narrated cases and developed pleadings and argued on some questions of law in courts on behalf of litigants. These were unlearned people in law but volunteered to assist the courts and litigants to settle pleadings and argue them in court at a fee.

They were later appointed as **sergeants at law** and it was from their rank that the word **barrister** first came up. The word **attorney** also came up to describe these barristers. This was during the reign of Edward I (1272-1307).³ These barristers were patronized by land owners and religious bodies. The word barrister was first mentioned in 1455.⁴ In the middle of 15th century, the word **solicitor** also came up to describe barristers who practice at the Court of Equity and the Chancery. By 17th century, solicitors are distinguished from attorneys or barristers.

In the 19th century, the distinction between attorney/barristers and solicitors was abolished.⁵

This time, there were no law school and no University to learn but there was in existence a system of **apprenticeship** from attorneys, barristers and solicitors. After some years of apprenticeship a person can be called to the bar in any of the available Inns of Court in England namely:

1. Inner Temple- Inaugurated in 1388⁶
2. Lincoln's Inn- Inaugurated in 1422⁷
3. Middle Temple- Inaugurated in 1573⁸
4. Gray's Inn- Inaugurated in 1597⁹

Apprenticeship was later combined with **teaching** at the inns.

¹ O. Adewoye Prelude to the legal profession in Lagos 1863-1880. (1970) Journal of African Law p98.

² O.B. Akinsola Principles of law in practice (2016) St. Paul publishing House Ibadan.p3

³ Ibid

⁴ Ibid

⁵ Ibid

⁶ www.innertemple.org.uk

⁷ www.Lincolnsinn.org.uk

⁸ www.middletemple.org.uk

⁹ www.graysinnhotel.com.ng

Teaching at the inn was abolished in 1642 leaving only apprenticeship in barrister's chambers and law firms.

By 1729, English law required 5 years training at barristers chambers for new lawyers.¹⁰

In America, the same system was in operation and products of this system were John Adams second president of America, John Marshall, Andrew Jackson and Thomas Jefferson.¹¹ The last two names were later presidents of America.

THE CHANGING POSITION IN ENGLAND

Apprenticeship was considered obsolete by Blackstone who was the first professor of law in England. But A.V Dicey was of the belief that apprenticeship was most appropriate and realistic.¹² Blackstone school of thought prevailed and a school of law was established in Oxford and he was appointed the first professor of common Law in Oxford University.

In 1758¹³ Blackstone said, **“that law could be thought as part of a broader education at a university rather than as a mechanical part of a business in an apprenticeship”** he said further that law could be considered at a university with a study of logic and reasoning, legal history, comparative law and experimental philosophy and the classics of Greece and Rome.¹⁴

The second law school was established at the University of Cambridge fifty years later.

Degree to be awarded in law was coined as LL.B at the University College London in 1826. By 1846 the House of Common legislated that law should be taught as a degree in Universities. Queens College started law degree in 1849. Students were taught from Blackstone Commentaries, Emmanuel Karts commentaries and Jeremy Bentham Treatise.

Queens College was awarding B.A in law and other disciplines as combined honours. Following the Queen's College example, B.A in Jurisprudence began in oxford in 1855, and Durham in 1858, Owen College in Manchester in 1880 and University College Liverpool in 1892.¹⁵

¹⁰ www.britanica.com>topic>legal...

¹¹ www.lawuchicago.edu>paths to law...

¹² www.britanica.com>topics>legal...

¹³ Ibid

¹⁴ Ibid

¹⁵ Ibid

LEGAL EDUCATION IN AMERICA

The first American law school was established in the College of William and Mary In Virginia in 1779 by **Thomas Jefferson** who was then the Governor of Virginia. He appointed **George Whytheas** the first professor of law in America. He formed a curriculum that combined the teaching of law with politics and government directed his students to visit the congress regularly. Law school was established in Harvard in 1869.

Oliver Wendel Homes was the second professor of law in America.¹⁶ Other countries emulated England and America by establishing law schools in their Universities.

LEGAL EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

The First faculty of law was University of Nigeria, Nsukka established in 1960 under Professor G.M Johnson.¹⁷ University of Lagos was established in 1962. The Faculty of law was pioneered by professor LCB Gower. ABU, faculty of law 1962 and OAU 1962. First Nigerian Professor of law was Professor TaslimOlawale Elias who was` from Lagos State ¹⁸ and first female Nigerian Professor of law was Professor JadesolaAkande.¹⁹ The University of Benin was established in1970 but started study of law in 1981. The Nigeria law school was also established in 1962.

WHO IS A LAW ACADEMIC OR WHO IS A LECTURER?²⁰

A lecturer is a person who gives lectures especially as an occupation at a University, polytechnic, monotechnic or College of Education. A lecturer is an academic who teaches, conducts research and leads research group.²¹

There are so many graduates in Nigeria but very few are interested in lecturing or teaching, while some who are interested in lecturing are not qualified to lecture because of their low grades. To be a lecturer, a good first degree is required with master or Doctor of Philosophy degree. A law lecturer that wants to be head of Department or Dean of Law must also be called to Bar having passed the Nigerian Law school

¹⁶ [Scholarship.law.win.edu>law school...](#)

¹⁷ [Law.unn.edu.ng>about>history](#)

¹⁸ [www.limeshighereducation.com>u...](#)

¹⁹ [Lasu.edu.ng](#)

²⁰ [www.prettylifestyle2.com>department...](#)

²¹ [www.thorougheducation.com>is-my...](#)

examination.

Lecturing in Nigeria Universities are classified into 7 positions ²² starting from:

Graduate Assistance	First Degree with First Class or Second Upper Division
Assistance Lecturer	Master Degree
Lecturer II	Master Degree or Ph.D
Lecturer I	Ph.D with years of experience
Senior Lecturer	Ph.D with years of experience
Associate Professor/Reader	Ph.D with years of experience
Professor	Ph.D with years of experience

The truth is lecturers earn a lot of money through teaching, research and grants. Lecturers can also freelance in other institutes on part time basis which make lecturing a good and lucrative job for people with the passion, knowledge and skills required for the job. Moon lighting should be avoided here. Background check is always conducted on a prospective lecturer in order for the new employer to know his antecedent (characterwise).

PROMOTION CRITERIA

MINIMUM NUMBER OF PAPERS REQUIRED FOR APPOINTMENT & PROMOTION OF ACADEMIC STAFF

LEVEL	MINIMUM NUMBER OF JOURNAL PAPERS
Graduate Assistance Lecturer	No paper required
Assistance Lecturer to Lecturer II(with Ph.D)	No paper Required
Assistance Lecturer to Lecturer II(without Ph.D)	One (1) journal paper and one (1) Refereed Proceedings
Lecturer II to Lecturer I (with Ph.D)	Three (3) journal papers OR Two (2) Journal

²² Federal University Oye Ekiti (Guideline for Appraisals, Appointment and promotion of Academic Staff. October 2014.

	papers and Refereed Proceedings
Lecturer II to Lecturer I (without Ph.D)	Five(5) Journal papers OR Three (3) Journal papers and Four (4) Refereed Proceedings
Lecturer I to Senior Lecturer (Ph.D) is compulsory as from this grade).	8 Journal Papers Of Which At Least Two (2) Must Be International Journals OR Six (6) Journal Papers Of Which At Least Two(2) Be Internationally Published Journals plus Four (4) Refereed Proceedings
Senior Lecturer to Reader	Fifteen (15) Journal papers of which at least Four (4) must be Internationally published Journals OR Thirteen (13) Journals which at least Four (4) must be Internationally published Journals and Four (4) Refereed Proceedings
Reader to Professor	Twenty (20) Journal papers of which at least Five (5) must be Internationally published Journals OR Eighteen (18) Journal papers which at least Five (5) must be Internationally published and Four (4) Refereed Proceedings. ²³

Note: this vary from University to University, the above is not Universal. Journal papers are now classified into Impact Journal, African Journal Online, Bibliography of African. Every lecturer writing paper for publication should find out stated of the Journal he is intending to publish his paper whether it is a predatory Journal obscure or high journal. The Journal papers must be spread across.

JOURNAL PUBLICATION

Appointment and promotion in academic is not like in civil service. The rule in academic is “**Publish or Perish**”. Pulication of research articles in Journals is a necessity. The article publication must be in a reputable journal, not an obscure, predatory and unrecognized journal. Journals are now classified into indexed Journal, non indexed Journal, Predatory and high impact Journal.

²³ Ibid p3.

Index Journals are journals that are of high quality and certified by indexing organizations such as SCOPUS, ISTOR, Hein online, African Journal online and Bibliography of African literature. Every lecturer writing paper for publication should find out the status of the journal he is intending to publish his paper.

There is also the requirement that certain percentage of your publications must be in local and international journals. It must also spread to many Universities, not just some selected few who you are friends. It must be peer reviewed journals and some Universities require that your journal publication must spread across the Universities in the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. You must beware of plagiarism by acknowledging the source of your information. Note that indexed and high impact journal earn higher marks in assessment for promotion among universities in Nigeria will only consider University based journals, not association journal, they may also take professional journals.

Your article must be original and must contribute to the knowledge. don't write cultivate the habit writing on overflogged issues but go to emerging areas, grey areas and where the law is recondite.

SELF SUSTENANCE IN ACADEMIC CAREER BY TOWING THE PATH OF HONOUR

Certain qualities are indispensable to keep yourself afloat in academics. These are integrity of results, examination and tests, On no account should a lecturer collaborate with students to involve in exam malpractice or changing of marks, or awarding undeserved marks to students due to any form of relationship. An academic worth his salt should not sexually harass female student. Punctuality to lectures, committee meetings and other assignments of the university are equally essential. A lecturer should shun sale of handouts, instead publish standard book by standard publishers. This is useful for your promotion apart from profit you will get from it. No form of extortion of students whether male or female, No sorting, No Moon lighting. (Earning double salaries by working in two places at the same time). No victimization of any student in marking and in invigilation of examination.

It is of utmost importance to have a role model among senior lecturers. You can adopt any senior academic as your role model and mentor. You can take regular advice from your mentor, you can take your lecture notes to him for vetting and editing, you can take your journal articles to him to vet and edit. You can also publish with your mentor, Respect your seniors and colleagues and have good relationship with staff and students.

Finally, you must be focused, don't allow money to derail you. Money will later come, make a niche,

carve a name for yourself in your lecturing style and in your research publications. Submit to team work and collaborate regularly with your colleagues. Cooperate and submit to departmental authorities, Dean's Office and the University Management.